

13 Reasons Why...

...you should use EOSC and its services

EOSC is a major European initiative designed to provide researchers, innovators, and institutions with seamless access to research data, services, and digital resources. By fostering an open and collaborative research environment, EOSC supports the principles of Open Science and enables the efficient sharing, management, and supports Open Science across disciplines and national borders.

As research becomes increasingly data-driven and interdisciplinary, there is a growing need for reliable infrastructure that facilitate collaboration, data accessibility, and advanced computational capabilities. EOSC addresses these challenges by offering a unified ecosystem that connects researchers with valuable resources while promoting FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data practices.

Access to Research Data

Find and reuse datasets from many scientific disciplines

Open Science Support

Helps researchers share results transparently

Collaboration Opportunities

Connects researchers, institutions, and projects across Europe

FAIR Data Practices

Promotes data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

Computing Resources

Provides access to cloud-based computing and analysis services

Cost Efficiency

Reduces the need for individual institutions to build all infrastructure themselves

Data Preservation

Supports long-term storage and accessibility of research outputs

Cross-disciplinary Research

Makes it easier to combine data and methods from different fields

Training and Skills Development

Offers learning resources and support for researchers

Europe-wide Ecosystem

Provides access to a large network of services, repositories, and research organizations

Compliance with Funding Requirements

Helps meet open-data and open-science mandates from many funders

Stronger International Competitiveness

EOSC helps European researchers and institutions remain competitive in the global research landscape.

Trusted Environment

Uses standards and governance designed for research communities

Find citations and scholarly resources on Open Data and other topics in the EOSC SOA Group Library on Zotero.

